

THE JOURNEY ACROSS THE AGES: A HISTORICAL OVERVIEW OF YOGA

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ABSTRACT: Yoga is a holistic practice that originated in the mythical land of ancient India thousands of years ago which encircles physical, mental and spiritual aspects of human that focuses on achieving harmony between body and soul. From the Vedas and Upanishadas to the profound insights of sage Patanjali, we will dive deep into the wisdom and teachings that have shaped yoga into what it is today. Yoga's origin is deeply rooted in the cultural and spiritual heritage of ancient India and developed over thousands of years through the contribution of great sages, yoga gurus and the philosophical traditions. The origin of yoga in India reflects its deep connection to the spiritual and philosophical tradition of ancient times which evolved as a means for individuals to attain self realisation, inner harmony and spiritual growth. There is yogic lore that says yoga has been as old as the dawn of civilization and it is believed to have originated around 5000to 6000 years ago. The origin, evolution and transition of yoga through the ages has been an interesting subject of study. Therefore, it is very significant to study the origin, history and the stages of the transition of yoga. This paper attempts to analyse the origin, history and evolution of yoga in India. To analyse this paper, both analytical and descriptive methods have been adopted by using secondary sources in the form of printed books, journals, research papers and articles.

Keywords: Yoga, History, Origin, Evolution, Transition, India.

INTRODUCTION: “Yoga is like music: the rhythm of the body, the melody of the mind and the harmony of the soul create the symphony of life”-B.K.S Iyenger.

Yoga is the art and science intimately linked to the coming together of the individual consciousness with the universal consciousness. Yoga often associated with physical postures (*asanas*) and breath control (*pranayama*) is a multifaced discipline that integrates spiritual, mental and physical practices. The term yoga has its roots in the Sanskrit word 'Yuj' which stands for union or yoke or joining. In the traditional terminology it is merging of the individual Self with the Universal Self. It is one of the six systems of Indian philosophy known as *Saddarsanas*. The objectives of the yoga is the self realisation to overcome all kinds of sufferings leading to the liberation (*Moksha*). It brings an individual closer to nature. Many yoga poses are even titled after nature and other living beings viz. cat pose, snake pose, eagle pose, lion pose, mountain pose which can make us to connect with nature. Yoga is the ancient science that originated in India and it is adopted by people in global arena for maintaining physical, emotional and mental well being. Yoga has a rich history of its growth, evolution and transition through the different period of history. When delving into the subject of yoga, one's initial thoughts goes towards the history of yoga and its evolution and transition from ancient to modern era.

OBJECTIVES: The primary objective of this research paper is to explore the historical background, origin, growth and evolution of yoga through the ages.

METHODOLOGY: Analytical and descriptive methods based on the secondary sources have been adopted for this study. The secondary data is collected from printed books, journals, research papers and articles and the websites.

DISCUSSION: The origin of the Yoga is deeply rooted in the cultural and spiritual heritage of ancient India. It developed over thousands of years through the contributions of various sages, teachers, and philosophical traditions. The origin of yoga in India reflects its deep connection to the spiritual and philosophical traditions of ancient times. It evolved as a means for individuals to attain self-realization, inner harmony and spiritual growth. Today, yoga has spread globally and is practiced by millions of people, embracing its physical, mental, and spiritual dimensions as a path of well-being and self-exploration. The practice of Yoga is believed to have started with the very dawn of

civilization. The development of yoga can be tracked back to over five thousand years ago, though few of the researchers speculate that yoga might be up to ten thousand years old. However, there are no proper evidences of the actual date of starting of yoga in India due to the lack of written records in the earliest period. The teachings of yoga had been passed on orally, memorized and recited. Gradually the principles and practices began to be recorded and in later years permanently and written tradition of recording the important aspects of yoga have been started. Yoga has been mentioned in the various sources and epics like Ramayana and Mahabharata and certain Tantric traditions. Hindus and Buddhists have adapted a disciplined Yogic lifestyle since its inception. Moreover, there was a primal or pure Yoga which has been manifested in mystical traditions of South Asia. During this period Yoga was being practised under the direct guidance of Guru and special emphasis was laid on its spiritual value. It was a part of prayer and yoga *sadhana* was inbuilt in their rituals. The worship of Sun was given highest importance during the Vedic period. The practice of *Surya Namaskara* may have been invented later due to this influence. Today teaching of Yoga is being imparted by many renowned institutions like Yoga Institutions, Yoga Colleges, Yoga Departments in the Universities, Naturopathy colleges and Private trusts & societies. Many Yoga Clinics, Yoga Therapy and Training Centres, Preventive Health Care Units of Yoga, Yoga Research Centres etc. have been established in hospitals and medical Institutions too.

Evolution of Yoga: Yoga has been part and parcel of man's activities and healthy and peaceful life since time immemorial. Yoga of today is very different from its traditional ancient ideas and practices. Many historians and scholars had done research on the different aspects of yoga and its transition through the ages and divided the stages of its evolution into stages with the help of which people can have idea on how the concept and ideas of yoga have changed with time. Historical research of various scholars proved that yoga was in existence in the pre Vedic period and the great yoga sage Patanjali systematised it through Patanjali yoga sutras. After him, many yoga gurus contributed a lot in this field. Yoga's prolonged affluent history can be divided into periods as follows.

- Pre-Vedic era
- Vedic Era
- Classical Era
- Post Classical Era
- Modern Era

Pre-Vedic Era: In the pre-Vedic era which dates back approximately 3000 B.C the archaeological excavations have revealed several fossils, figurines, and seals depicting various *asanas* and techniques of *pranayama* and *dhyana*. It is believed that Lord Shiva took the form of *Adiyogi* or the first Yoga Guru. He shared detailed knowledge of Yoga with the seven great sages (*Saptarishi*) of the time, at the banks of Kantisarovar. The Sages had travelled throughout many places and propagated this valuable knowledge on Yoga with others. Several excavation sites along the Indus Valley civilization has supported this legend of Lord Shiva being the *Adiyogi*. The great effort of the Saptarishi helped to implant Yoga gradually into the lives and culture of various people. There is an ancient form of pure Yoga or primordial yoga that was mystical in origin and was prevalent in southern Asia during the pre-Vedic era. In the Indus Valley civilization which thrived around 3000 to 1500 B.C., several seals and fossils depicting figures in yogic postures have been found in the excavation which suggested the existence of early forms of Yoga. Archaeologist have found evidences from this period the statues and art work that shows that Lord Shiva adopted yogic posture which shows that He is meditating by using asana poses. The phallic symbols, seals of image of Mother Goddess are suggestive of Tantra Yoga. This Tantra Yoga was known for its connection with spiritual realm and techniques directing people for spiritual journey.

Vedic Era: The Vedic period represents the early stages of Indian civilization characterized by the composition of the Vedas which are followed by four sub-Vedas and Upangas (sub components). It was an era of profound philosophical inquiry, ritualistic practices and the development of foundational concepts which would influence the evolution of yoga. The four Vedas written in the Sanskrit language had described the ethics and principles to live a righteous and ethical life. Rigveda is first known text to contain information on yoga. In the Atharva Veda again, there is the

mention of the significance of the control of the breath. The Vedas depict yoga as means to balance mental, physical and spiritual life of the human. This era saw the consciousness of the role of yoga in the spiritual journey of the people. The Vedic period laid the foundational groundwork for the evolution of yoga as a spiritual, philosophical, and practical discipline. From the hymns of the Rigveda to the metaphysical exploration of the Upanishads and the ritualistic practices of the Yajurveda, yoga's origins are enmeshed with India's ancient spiritual heritage. The philosophy of karma, reincarnation, and the quest for self-realization provided a fertile ground for the yogic practices which aimed at achieving inner conversion towards spiritual liberation. In the religious scripture of Upanishadas, there is a way to get rid of pain. There prevailed two schools of yoga viz. *karma* and wisdom. The Bhagawat Gita mainly talks about various ways of communication with divinity including Wanga yoga, love yoga, karma yoga and wisdom yoga.

Classical Period: Around 500-800 A.D. has been considered as the classical and the most fertile and significant period of the growth and evolution of yoga history. During this period, commentaries of Vyasa on Yoga Sutras and Bhagawat Gita etc. came into existence. This period is mainly dedicated to two great spiritual gurus- Mahabir and Buddha. The principle of *Panch-Mahavrata* (five great vows) by Mahabir and the *Astha Marga* (eightfold path) by Budhdha can be recognised as the early nature of yoga practices. The period (200-400 CE) witnessed the rise of the most prominent yoga guru Patanjali who was one to systematise the concept and practice of yoga. He is considered as the father of modern yoga and gained a significant influence over the growth and evolution of yoga which has still continued with same vigour. Patanjali's Yoga Sutras portrayed on eight limbs of yoga which included *yamas*, *niyamas*, *asanas*, *pranayama*, *pratyahara*, *dharana*, *dhyana* and *samadhi* towards enlightenment scooping thoughts from Upanishadas and Bhagawatgita. Patanjali's Sutras highlights the psychological techniques to experience and gain the ultimate reality of the *asanas* (sitting postures). Patanjali in his iconic Yoga Sutras drew together large number of philosophical texts and articles. This Yoga Sutras were intended to be a decisive guide and the Bible of

yoga teaching and practice in modern time. This period emphasized the importance of the mind in yoga.

Post-Classical Period: The period between 800-1700 A.D. has been considered as the post classical period wherein greater emphasis was laid on the physical aspects of yoga. However, the focus and importance of yoga to rejuvenate and refresh the mind, body and soul, contribute to a healthier life came in the beginning of the 20th century. The teachings of great Acharyatrayas-Adi Shankracharya, Ramanujacharya, Madhavacharya-were prominent during this period. In this era many Yogis and philosophers such as Adi Sankaracharya contributed for the development of Raja Yoga and Jnana Yoga which can led people for the path of liberation. For rejuvenation of the mind, meditation was also considered so vital. The teachings of Suradasa, Tulasidasa, Purandardasa, Mirabai had significant contribution during this period. Matsyendaranatha, Gorkshanatha, Cauranginatha, Swatmaram Suri, Gheranda, Shrinivasa Bhatt are some of the eminent gurus who popularized and highlighted the importance of the Hatha Yoga practices among the masses to live a healthier life. The post classical yoga witnessed the rise of the popularity of Tantra Yoga which was very crucial to the development of modern yoga. This kind of yoga has spotlighted the significance of cleansing and exhilarating the mind and the body and intensified the consciousness to go beyond the individual and social tabus.

Modern Era: The 19th and 20th centuries witnessed a revitalization of yoga in India. Yogis like Ramana Maharshi, Ramakrishna Paramhansa, Yogananda, Vivekananda, B.K.S Iyengar, K. Pattabhi Jois who had contributed a lot for the development of Raja Yoga, Hatha Yoga, Vedanta Yoga and Bhakti Yoga. This period focused on yoga as means of physical well-being. Now in the contemporary times, everybody has conviction about yoga practices towards the preservation, maintenance of health. Swami Vivekananda was largely responsible for propagating yoga in the west. His teachings at the Parliament of Religion in Chicago in 1893 introduced yoga to the Western world. In addition to that, Yoga has been spread all over the globe by the teachings of great personalities like Swami Shivananda, Shri T. Krishnamacharya, Swami Kuvalayananda,

Shri Yogendara, Swami Rama, Sri Aurobindo, Maharshi Mahesh Yogi, Acharya Rajanish, K. Pattabhi Jois, BKS. Iyengar, Swami Satyananda Sarasvati and others.

In the later part of 20th century till today, yoga gained widespread popularity in the West, characterized by the focus on physical fitness and stress management. This period witnessed the emergence of certain yoga styles like Astanga, Iyenger, Bikram and Vinyasa. Now yoga become globalised with millions of followers worldwide who have explored the benefits of both physical, spiritual and mental well-being.

However, some Critics have argued that due to the commercialisation of yoga, it has been stripped of its spiritual essence and cultural authenticity, yet adherents believe that its easy accessibility provide benefits to the larger masses for healthy and peaceful life. Today yoga is integrated with medical settings as complementary therapy for the stress and depression management and relieving from various chronic diseases highlighting holistic approach to healthy life.

CONCLUSION:

Yoga is the ancient science of practices which originated in India and is now adopted by people globally to maintain physical, emotional and mental health. It is one of the most ancient practices in the world. From its ancient roots in India to global arena in the recent era, yoga has evolved into a diverse and multifaceted discipline that inspire and provide benefits to the millions of people of the globe. Throughout its long history, the ideas, beliefs and practices of yoga have passed through transition and evolution. This tradition of yoga has absorbed (or mixed) different practices and philosophies of various stages. Today there are various branches of yoga, each with its own ideological principles and philosophies and the ways of practising in different perspectives of global world. But there can be no doubt that despite whichever particular kind of yoga is followed, it can bring many benefits regarding the physical, mental and spiritual arena of human life. In the atmosphere of chaos and disturbances, many people have adopted yoga as a means of searching peace for their mind and soul by managing the stresses and strains of life and lived a peaceful and happy life.

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